

Integrating outcrop and subsurface data to improve the predictability of geobodies distribution using a 3D training image: A case study of a Triassic Channel – Crevasse-splay complex

 The corrections made in this section will be reviewed and approved by a journal production editor.

Luis Miguel **Yeste**^{a,*} lmyste@ugr.es, Ricardo **Palomino**^b, Augusto Nicolás **Varela**^{c,d}, Neil David **McDougal**^e, César **Viseras**^a

^aSedimentary Reservoir Workgroup (SEDREGROUP), Department of Stratigraphy and Palaeontology, Facultad de Ciencias, S/N 18003, University of Granada, Granada, Spain

^bRepsol Exploración S.A., Méndez Álvaro, 44, 28045, Madrid, Spain

^cY-TEC S.A, Av. del Petróleo s/n (1923), Berisso, Argentina

^dConsejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Calle 8 1467, B1904, La Plata, Buenos Aires, Argentina

^eConsultant Sedimentology and Stratigrapher, 28290, Madrid, Spain

*Corresponding author.

Abstract

Fluvial sandstones deposited by high-sinuosity fluvial systems are one of the most complex reservoirs to predict and model with confidence, a reflection of both the geometries and complex distribution of the component geobodies. By integrating both analogue outcrop data and associated subsurface data, as well as new technical advances in the reconstruction of the outcrop in 3D (Digital Outcrop Models, DOM), the geostatistical parameters, which condition the modelling of these reservoirs, can be better determined. In addition, DOMs also allow us to easily extract the necessary georeferenced input data (digitized outcrop interpretations, geometrical parameters, as well as key surfaces) and so create geocellular outcrop models (GOM); a useful tool with which to contrast the results obtained from geostatistical simulations, as well as to quantify the uncertainty associated with the results. In this study, classical field data, digital data derived from outcrop models and subsurface data were combined in order to carry out a geostatistical modelling of a Channel – Crevasse-splay complex outcrop analogue, located in the Triassic Red Beds of Iberian Meseta (TIBEM). Geostatistical modelling results were obtained by combining Object-based (OBM) and MultiPoint Statistics-based (MPS) modelling techniques. A critical element in this study was the design of appropriate modelling workflows with Petrel® which would best reproduce the distribution of heterogeneities at macroscale. The designed modelling workflow was used to construct a 3D Training Image (TI) of a fluvial reservoir comprising both a meandering channel system and its associated overbank sandstone deposits. The resulting TI represents all geobodies described in the studied outcrop example and is exportable to similar fluvial reservoirs. This TI was then used in MPS simulations, in order to establish how it could assist in the prediction of the reservoir geobodies, as well as confirming to what extent this prediction matched the outcrop.

Keywords: Multi-point statistics; Training images; Object-based modelling; Digital outcrop model; Meandering fluvial system; Crevasse splay; Heterogeneity; Outcrop/behind outcrop characterisation; TIBEM; Triassic

1 Introduction

In fluvial reservoirs, heterogeneity and connectivity of hydraulic properties are related to the geometry of geobodies and facies distributions (e.g. [Anderson, 1989](#); [Koltermann and Gorelick, 1996](#); [Davis et al., 1997](#); [Klingbeil et al., 1999](#); [Weissmann and Fogg., 1999](#); [Gaud et al., 2004](#), [Pranter and Sommer, 2011](#); [Deschamps et al., 2012](#); [Cabello et al., 2018](#); [Viseras et al., 2018](#); [Yeste et al., 2019, 2020](#); [Puig et al., 2019](#)). Specifically, the sedimentary dynamics of high-sinuosity fluvial systems give rise to highly complex and heterogeneous reservoirs. These systems are therefore very difficult to model given their inherent high degree of uncertainty, reflecting the great variety of geometries and the wide range of possibilities in the distribution of geobodies. This problem is amplified when the input data in the model are scarce, which is typically the case in subsurface-based studies. The study of outcrop analogues is therefore essential if we are to cover these gaps.

“Traditional” field data collection in outcrop analogues (e.g. sedimentological logs, geological maps and cross-sections) provides invaluable knowledge with which to characterize subsurface reservoirs (e.g. depositional systems, stratigraphic and paleogeographical syntheses). However, it is often difficult to extract reliable quantitative data on the geometries and spatial heterogeneities of sedimentary geobodies, data which are essential for 3D geostatistical reservoir modelling (e.g. [Krum and Johnson, 1993](#); [Bryant et al., 2000](#); [Deutsch, 2002](#); [Rarity et al., 2014](#)). New advances in digital techniques and data capture for outcrop analysis, such as digital outcrop models (DOM), are covering this gap. DOMs now offer an extremely useful tool for reservoir characterization, allowing for a precise and quantitative analysis of the geological exposure (e.g. [Enge et al., 2007](#); [Howell et al., 2014](#); [Rarity et al., 2014](#); [Cabello et al., 2018](#); [Yeste et al., 2020](#)). Additionally, when the outcrop-based study is complemented with subsurface information (e.g. core and well logs data), a complete dataset is obtained providing an accurate control of the distribution of the heterogeneities in outcrop analogues by direct validation of 1D data (core) with 3D data (outcrop-based data). This methodology is known as Outcrop/Behind Outcrop (OBO) characterization ([Donselaar and Schmidt, 2005](#); [Slatt et al., 2012](#); [Henaes et al., 2016](#); [Viseras et al., 2018](#); [Yeste et al., 2019, 2020](#)).

On the other hand, recent improvements in reservoir modelling capabilities and computational capacity provide an opportunity to input reservoir models with more accurate sedimentological data and to obtain more geologically consistent representations. This leads to different modelling opportunities, such as building large geocellular models, unlocking the possibility of representing reservoir heterogeneity in greater detail; or the realization of a high number (tens to hundreds) of equiprobable and alternative scenarios in an attempt to capture the reservoir uncertainties. However, independently of the modelling approach, accurate sedimentological models derived from outcrop analogues assume an even greater importance given that their characteristics can now be extracted with high precision.

Outcrop analogues provide both ‘hard’ (geometry and dimensions of geobodies) and ‘soft’ (knowledge and understanding of sedimentary depositional systems) data that are routinely used to improve our understanding of the subsurface, which is heavily under-sampled ([Howell et al., 2014](#)). In this context, outcrop analogues play a valuable role in steering geomodellers towards appropriate levels of geological detail.

There are three major conventional geostatistical techniques currently used in the modelling of fluvial reservoirs: Sequential-Indicator Simulation-Based modelling (SIS), Object-Based Modelling (OBM) and Multi-point statistics-based modelling (MPS). SIS-Based modelling is one of the most commonly used cell-based techniques, it uses a two-point approach and populates a model volume using variograms derived from one- or two-dimensional data ([Deutsch and Journal, 1992](#); [Seifert and Jensen, 1999a, b, 2000a, b](#); [Martinius et al., 2017](#)). Object-Based modelling (OBM) involves the population of a volume by objects with different geometries and dimensions replacing a background ([Clemetsen et al., 1990](#); [Deutsch and Wang, 1996](#); [Holden et al., 1998](#); [Deutsch and Tran, 2002](#)). By incorporating the outcrop/behind outcrop characterization together with the object-based modelling it is possible to reproduce the different geobody types, including their dimensions, distribution, as well as the facies and the relationship between them. This method can be used to generate a mathematical pattern ([Guardiano and Srivastava, 1993](#); [Strebelle, 2002](#); [Falivene et al., 2006](#); [Maharaja, 2008](#); [Pyrzcz et al., 2008](#); [Daly and Caers, 2010](#); [Mariethoz and Caers, 2015](#); [Pickel et al., 2015](#); [Mitten et al., 2020](#)), called the training image (TI). When the TI is used as input in the Multi-point Statistics (MPS)-based modelling process it combines the strengths of both OBM and cell-based models (such as SIS-Based

modelling). This produces facies models that are geologically realistic, allows for flexibility and are able to honour the geostatistics conditioned by the input data (Caers and Zhang, 2004; Strebelle and Levy, 2008; Le Coz et al., 2011; Hu et al., 2014; Zhou et al., 2018).

This study focuses on the reproduction by geostatistical techniques of geobody distribution within a high-sinuosity fluvial system outcrop example characterised by meandering channels and their associated overbank deposits (crevasse-splay deposits). The term ‘geobody’, as used in this study, refers to the geological elements in a reservoir. These elements are defined on the basis of their specific geometry (including width, thickness and orientation), bounding surfaces, internal sedimentary features (lithofacies and/or facies associations) and the location within the depositional environment. This is a term commonly used in geological modelling. Geobody is also equivalent to ‘architectural element’ as defined by Miall (1985), ‘depositional elements’ defined by Kostic and Aigner (2007) or the storeys of Ford and Pyles (2014).

The studied example is a succession located in the Triassic Red Beds of Iberian Meseta (TIBEM; Viseras et al., 2011, 2018; Henares et al., 2014, 2016; Yeste et al., 2019, 2020), often considered as an outcrop analogue for other hydrocarbon-productive reservoirs such as the Algerian TAGI (Trias Argilo-Greseux Inferieur; Rossi et al., 2002; Dabrio et al., 2005; Viseras et al., 2011; Henares et al., 2014, 2016; Viseras et al., 2018). The high-resolution sedimentological study of the M-S Unit in the selected TIBEM succession, integrating both outcrop and subsurface data, previously published by Yeste et al. (2020), will be the basis for this study.

The main goal of this research is to present a new modelling strategy using object-based modelling (OBM) for a high-sinuosity fluvial system outcrop analogue, applicable in the generation of training images (TI), and which would best reproduce the distribution of heterogeneities at macroscale. In addition, this modelling strategy, as well as the resulting 3D TI, is compared directly with the outcrop to evaluate the uncertainty in geobody prediction, showing a new application of Digital Outcrop Models (DOM), as well as demonstrating the value of outcrop analogues in the evaluation and prediction of the subsurface. These goals will be addressed through the following specific objectives: (1) design an appropriate modelling workflow with Petrel® to best reproduce the distribution of heterogeneities, at the scale of geobodies, and which are exportable to other examples of high-sinuosity fluvial systems; (2) to construct a 3D training image, based on both outcrop and subsurface data, for a high-sinuosity system characterized by meandering channels and crevasse-splay deposits and, also, exportable to other reservoirs of the same type; (3) to create MPS simulations using the constructed 3D TI, in order to establish how this can help in the prediction of the reservoir geobodies, as well as evaluating how this prediction matches to the studied outcrop. In addition, several scenarios will be created in order to establish how input data influence the improvement of reservoir prediction using MPS-based modelling.

2 Geological settings and sedimentological framework

The extensive Triassic Red Beds succession of the Iberian Meseta, south-central Spain (the TIBEM of Viseras et al., 2011, 2018; Henares et al., 2014, 2016; Yeste et al., 2019, 2020) are continental deposits which accumulated during the Tethyan rifting process (Late Permian-Upper Triassic; López-Gómez et al., 2019). The study area, located to the east of Alcaraz village (Albacete Province; Fig. 1A), corresponds to the most distal part of the outcropping TIBEM, as suggested by paleocurrent data (Fernández and Dabrio, 1985; Henares et al., 2014).

alt-text: Fig. 1

Fig. 1

(A) Location of the study area (Alcaraz village, Albacete province, Spain) showing the location of the studied outcrops. The orange shading represents the outcropping study area and the area covered by Digital Outcrop Models (DOM). Yellow points represent the location of sedimentological logs constructed to enable the characterization of lateral and vertical variability, respectively. Green points are well locations. Acronyms correspond to the names of profiles and wells, as explained in the text. (B) Synthetic stratigraphic succession of the selected study area (eastern of Alcaraz village). M-S Unit: Mudstone-Sandstone Unit; S Unit: Sandstone Unit; H Unit: Heterolithic Unit; M-E Unit: Mudstone-Evaporitic Unit. The rectangle indicates the approximate position of the selected stratigraphic interval for this study. (C) Digital outcrop model showing the location of the stratigraphic interval selected for modelling within the M-S Unit stratigraphic framework of study area. Also shown in (C) are key selected outcrops, sedimentary logs and well locations. [\(For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.\)](#)

The TIBEM succession in the study area thus comprises fluvial to coastal deposits within a linked stratigraphic framework. In this area, the ca. 160 m-thick sedimentary succession (Ladinian-Norian) is divided into four informal member-rank lithostratigraphic units (Yeste et al., 2019, 2020, Fig. 1B). From base to top, they are: (i) a mudstone-sandstone unit (M-S Unit), that includes both a meandering channel system and overbank sandstone deposits embedded in distal floodplain mudstones (Yeste et al., 2020); (ii) a sandstone unit (S Unit) corresponding to a braided system (Yeste et al., 2019); (iii) a heterolithic unit (H Unit) comprising alternating sandstone and mudstone layers deposited in a fluvio-marine transition zone (Yeste et al., 2017; García-García et al., 2017); and (iv) a mudstone-evaporitic unit (M-E Unit) composed of silt-rich coastal plain facies and intertidal sabkha evaporites. Pre-existing interpretations of the Triassic Red Beds by both Fernández (1977), which divided the succession into Sequences I to IV, and Arche and López-Gómez (2014), which divided the succession on the basis of the classic Germanic Trias Units (Keuper; K1 to K5), are here avoided in order to focus the chosen stratigraphy on the purely descriptive basis of lithology and sedimentological features.

The Mudstone-Sandstone Unit (M-S Unit) was selected for this study. This Unit, at least 90 m thick, occurs at the base of the TIBEM stratigraphic succession in the study area (Fig. 1B). The lower boundary was not observed in either outcrop or subsurface data in the study area, although its onlap across Palaeozoic paleorelief is observed in nearby outcrops. The M-S Unit is characterized by a low net-to-gross, effectively a sand:mud ratio of 10:90. It comprises lenticular, sand-prone packages up to 4 m thick, as well as thin, tabular, sand-prone packages, up to 2 m thick, encased within mud-prone sediments (Fig. 1B). The main depositional environment is interpreted as a high-sinuosity fluvial system, characterized by meandering channels and associated overbank deposits (crevasse-splays) encased within argillaceous floodplain deposits (Yeste et al., 2020).

A high-resolution sedimentological study of the M-S Unit, integrating both outcrop and subsurface data, was published by Yeste et al. (2020). In this previous study, a total of eighteen lithofacies were identified, grouped into ten facies associations: main channel (FA 1), point bar (FA 2), scroll bar (FA 3), chute channel (FA 4), crevasse channel (FA 5), proximal crevasse-splay (FA 6), medial crevasse-splay (FA 7), distal crevasse-splay (FA 8), distal floodplain (FA 9) and

swamp (FA 10). In addition, a robust conceptual model with predictive potential, establishing the three-dimensional stacking of facies, distribution of heterogeneities, and the connectivity between reservoir rock geobodies of both primary (channel) and secondary (crevasse complex), was also presented by Yeste et al. (2020). This conceptual model will be the basis for this study.

3 Methodological workflow

The data acquisition workflow and methodologies applied in this study can be grouped in two key elements (Fig. 2): (1) Outcrop/Behind Outcrop (OBO) methodology and (2) reservoir modelling.

Outcrop/Behind Outcrop methodology is a multi-approach technique that consists of data collection in both the outcrop and subsurface of a selected location. This technique includes, in turn, different methodologies at different study scales (macro-, meso and micro-scale). Two large groups of data are acquired with this methodology: outcrop- and subsurface-derived data.

Firstly, an outcrop-based study was undertaken with the aim of describing the sedimentological characteristics of the selected outcrops, aimed principally at the identification and description of the main architectural elements or geobodies, in terms of geometry, internal structure, facies analysis and both the vertical and lateral relationship with other geobodies. In addition, this phase also included the 3D reconstruction of outcrops (digital outcrop models or DOM), a task made possible by new technical advances in photogrammetry with RPAS (Remotely Piloted Aircraft System) designed to complement the outcrop-based observations.

In a second phase, subsurface data was acquired directly behind the selected outcrops. These data include continuous core recovery and well log data. Well log data include the Gamma Ray log (GR) in addition to borehole imaging from Optical and Acoustic Televiewers (OBI and ABI, respectively). The ABI is a slim-hole logging tool with an ultrasonic transducer sensor. This tool provides a 360° oriented acoustic image (amplitude and travel time). The OBI is a slim-hole logging tool with a high sensitivity digital image sensor. This tool provides a 360° RGB true colour-oriented image. Dip tadpoles, together with GR pattern analyses, provide information on the spatial distribution, orientation and dip of the main sedimentary surfaces and structures.

The final phase of this part of the study workflow was the integration of both outcrop and subsurface data (OBO characterisation; Fig. 2), in order to establish those key characteristics that: (a) assist in the identification of the geobodies and determine the spatial distribution of the heterogeneities that delimit these geobodies for a specific depositional environment; and (b) the generation of quantitative conceptual models and paleogeographic maps which summarise the spatial distribution of the identified geobodies.

The results of OBO characterisation were the input data for the second methodological phase of this study; reservoir modelling (Fig. 2). Reservoir modelling is the broad term for a set of processes which typically aim to integrate all available geoscience data and interpretations, into a 3D volume, discretized into 3D cells, with the aim of modelling or predicting rock heterogeneities and petrophysical properties within the framework of necessarily incomplete data typical of subsurface contexts (Ma, 2019). This process, known as static reservoir modelling, consists of assigning facies types and petrophysical property values using statistically-based methods which require input data to geometrically define the reservoir and condition modelling of key properties. The result is a 3D model that describes the main characteristics of the reservoir in terms of its facies distribution, petrophysical properties and volumetrics. In this study, the reservoir modelling process has focused only on the geostatistical modelling of facies at meso-scale.

In the following sections, data and methods used for OBO characterization (section 4.1), as well as data and methods used to both to define the geometry of the 3D model and to define the 3D distribution of geobodies (section 5), are described.

4 OBO characterisation: data, methods and results

4.1 Data and methods

The applied OBO characterisation workflow includes detailed sedimentological description from both surface (“classical” outcrop-derived and digital outcrop-derived observations plus measurements) and subsurface (cores and well logging) data. Specifically, data from a 0.813 km² outcropping area (approximately 5 km length of outcropping cliff), a total of 20 sedimentological logs (CP0, CPMR1 to CPMR8, CPML1 to CPML9 and CBML1 to CBML2) and 5 wells (MB1 to MB4 and S2P3) were employed in this study (Fig. 1A).

The results from the OBO characterisation workflow used in this study are published in Yeste et al. (2020). For the subsequent reservoir modelling phase, described in this paper (Fig. 2), it was first necessary to establish, and also to quantify, the lateral variability of facies and their relationship with the described geobodies, one stratigraphic interval was selected (Fig. 1C). This interval was selected on the basis of: (1) exceptional 3D outcrop features and significant lateral continuity, (2) the presence of geobodies, outcropping in different locations at the selected stratigraphic interval, (3) well-established relationships between the different geobodies, and (4) the selected interval has also been drilled by 5 wells (MB1 to MB4 and S2P3).

In addition, a Digital Outcrop Model (DOM), covering the total outcropping area, has been created in order to complete the outcrop-derived measurement dataset and digitize outcrop interpretations (Fig. 1A). The DOM was created using the Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetric technique. A Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS), equipped

with a Sony ILCE-5000 camera with a resolution of 20.1 megapixels, was used for image acquisition and two high-precision GPS devices were used for Ground Control Points (GCP) acquisition. Two specific software applications were used: MiKroKopter-Tool® software, used for flight planning; and Agisoft Metashape Professional® software, used in building the DOMs from SfM photogrammetry. The mean resolution of the resulting DOM is 1 cm/pixel.

Once the DOM is built, it was imported into the specific DOM interpretation software. For this study the Virtual Reality Geological Studio (VRGS®) software application was used (Hodgetts, 2010). In this step, the outcrop interpretations developed during the fieldwork stage were digitized; specifically, geobody mapping, facies and facies associations mapping, as well as the bounding surfaces of the geobodies and any key stratigraphic surfaces. The geometric parameters (shape, thickness and width) of the identified geobodies were also extracted, as well as measurements of paleocurrents to complete the field observations. In this way, all the interpretations that characterize the outcrop are perfectly georeferenced.

4.2 Geobody characterization and facies distribution

For the purposes of the present study, modelling the distribution of heterogeneities; and considering the limitations of the algorithms, it is not possible to support an excessive number of variables (fewer than eight; Ma, 2019). As such, the 10 facies associations described by Yeste et al. (2020) are grouped in four geobody types (Table 1): CH (meandering channel fill), PB (point bar deposits), CS (crevasse-splay deposits) and FP (floodplain deposits).

alt-text: Table 1

Table 1

 The table layout displayed in this section is not how it will appear in the final version. The representation below is solely purposed for providing corrections to the table. To preview the actual presentation of the table, please view the Proof.

Summary of geobodies identified in the M-S Unit for this study. Geometry, thickness, width (lateral extension measured perpendicular to the main flow direction of the channel belt) and Lithofacies are shown for each geobody. The relationships of each geobody with facies associations described by Yeste et al., 2020) is also shown. Lithofacies: Gm (mudstone rip-up clast conglomerate); Sh (fine to medium grained, horizontal laminated sand); St (fine to medium grained, trough cross bedding sand); Sr (very fine-to fine-grained, current ripple laminated sand); Sc (very fine-to fine-grained, climbing ripple laminated sand); Sd (very fine-grained, syn-sedimentary deformed sand); Lm (massive silt with presence of pedofeatures); Ll (horizontal laminated or uneven laminated silt); Fm (massive clay with presence of pedofeatures); Fl (horizontal or uneven laminated clay); Cm (massive micritic mudstones).

Geobody	Geometry	Thickness	Width	Facies Associations (from Yeste et al., 2020)	Lithofacies
Channel (CH)	Lenticular	Up to 3 m	Up to 40 m	Main channel (FA 1)	Gm, St, Sr, Fl
Point bar (PB)	Sigmoidal	Up to 3.6 m	Up to 130 m	Lower and middle point bar (FA 2), Scroll bar (FA 3), Chute channel (FA 4)	Gm, St, Sr
Crevasse-splay (CS)	Lobular	Up to 2 m	Up to 230 m	Crevasse channel (FA 5), Proximal to Distal crevasse-splay (FA 6, FA 7, FA 8; respectively)	Sh, Sr, Sc, Sd, Ll, Lm
Floodplain (FP)	Tabular	Up to 10 m	100–1000 m	Distal floodplain (FA 9), Swamp (FA 10)	Fm, Fl, Cm

4.2.1 Geobody CH: meandering channel fill

Geobody CH, composed only of FA 1, occurs as channel-shaped bodies up to 3 m thick with a lateral extension of up to 40 m perpendicular to the main paleoflow direction (Fig. 3A–B, Table 1). They are characterised by a concave-up erosive base, whilst the top surface of the geobody is horizontal and sharp (Fig. 3B). CH geobodies are sandstone-dominated and also characterised by a fining-upwards grain-size trend often with pebbly mudstones (Lithofacies Gm) as basal lags (Fig. 3C). Overlying the basal lags are medium to fine-grained sandstones with trough cross-bedding (Lithofacies St) and very fine-grained sandstone with current ripples (Lithofacies Sr) towards the top. Locally, these geobodies also show a final interval of laminated fine-grained (siltstone and mudstone) deposits (Lithofacies Fl).

Digital outcrop model and well data (core description and gamma ray log; GR log) of Outcrop CH-PB. (A) Digital outcrop model of Outcrop CH-PB showing well locations, (B) Interpreted digital outcrop model of Outcrop CH-PB showing width, thickness and orientation measurements for both Geobodies CH and PB, (C) GR log and core description for Well MB 4, principally comprising Geobody CH and (D) GR log and core description for Well MB 3, consisting largely of Geobody PB.

The fining-upward succession, together with the channelized geometries and erosive lower surfaces suggest that CH geobodies should be interpreted as the deposits of meandering channels (Viseras et al., 2018; Yeste et al., 2020). The basal pebble lag (Lithofacies Gm) represents thalweg lag deposits (Bridge, 1993, 2003; Ghinassi et al., 2014; Viseras et al., 2018; Yeste et al., 2020). The stacking of Lithofacies St and Sr reflects a gradual channel abandonment. The occasional presence of laminated fine-grained deposits (Lithofacies Fl) is interpreted as a mud plug due to neck cut-off of a meandering channel, suggesting a high sinuosity meandering channel (Viseras et al., 2018).

4.2.2 Geobody PB: point bar deposits

PB geobodies occur as asymmetrical, sigmoidal-shaped bodies, up to 3.6 m thick and with lateral extensions of up to 130 m (Table 1). These bodies are typically bounded by horizontal and erosive bases, whilst the tops are horizontal and sharp (Fig. 3A–B). As shown by Yeste et al. (2020), both point bar (FA 2) and scroll bar (FA 3) facies associations are genetically related. In addition, the chute channel (FA 4) facies association is a small-scale element gradational into the scroll bar facies associations. For this reason, these three facies associations (FA 2 to FA 4) were merged into the PB geobody.

PB geobodies are sand-dominated characterised by a fining-upward facies sequence passing from mudstone rip-up clast conglomerate (Lithofacies Gm) to very fine-grained sandstones (Lithofacies St and Sr; Fig. 3D). These geobodies typically display several inclined master bedding surfaces dipping towards the channel fill centre (epsilon cross-bedding *sensu* Allen, 1963), which extends from base to top of the geobody, and delineates bedsets (*sensu* Ghinassi et al., 2014). Internally, these bedsets are characterised by trough cross-bedding (Lithofacies St) and current ripples (Lithofacies Sr) towards the top of the facies sequence. Occasionally, conglomerate, with pebbly mudstone (Lithofacies Gm), occurs at the base. Locally, mud drapes occur between the inclined master surfaces, both as layers within the packages and as drapes over the inclined master surfaces.

The asymmetrical sigmoidal geometries together with the characteristic occurrence of several inclined surfaces perpendicular to the paleocurrent and the fining-upward succession suggest that PB geobodies should be interpreted as point bar deposits. The low angle inclined surfaces are thus interpreted as lateral accretion surfaces. Basal pebble lags (Lithofacies Gm) are accordingly attributed to deposition in the pool zone of a laterally migrating channel thalweg. The occurrence of mud drapes between the lateral accretion surfaces represents deposition during a waning flood stage (Thomas et al., 1987; Viseras et al., 2018).

4.2.3 Geobody CS: crevasse-splay deposits

CS geobodies occur as lobe-shape bodies, up to 2 m thick and up to 230 m in lateral extension, perpendicular to the main paleoflow direction (Table 1). These lobate bodies are characterized by a horizontal, sharp base, whilst the tops are convex-up and sharp (Fig. 4A–B). Four component facies associations were distinguished by Yeste et al. (2020): crevasse channels (FA 5), proximal crevasse-splay (FA 6), medial crevasse-splay (FA 7) and distal crevasse-splay (FA 8). With the aim of better modelling the distribution of heterogeneities, but also considering the practical limits of the algorithms, these four facies associations were grouped first into a single lower order geobody (CS) and then into two finer-scale geobodies: proximal crevasse-splay geobodies (CSp), characterised by high-energy facies associations (FA 5 and FA 6); and distal crevasse-splay geobodies (CSd), characterised by low-energy facies associations (FA 7 and FA 8).

CSp geobodies, with up to 2 m of thickness and 130 m of lateral extension, perpendicular to the main flow direction of the channel belt and from their insertion point (channel margin), are characterised by horizontal laminated (Lithofacies Sh) to trough cross-bedded (Lithofacies St) and/or current rippled sandstones (Lithofacies Sr). Towards the top of these geobodies, climbing ripple cross-laminated sandstones (Lithofacies Sc) are also recognized (Fig. 4C). Commonly, small lenticular bodies, up to 1.1 m thick and up to 6 m width, appear within these geobodies (Fig. 4B). These display concave-up, erosive bases and horizontal, sharp tops, and are characterised by thin mudstone rip-up clast conglomerates as basal lags overlain by fine to very fine-grained sandstone with trough cross-bedding (Lithofacies St) and very fine-grained sandstone with current ripples (Lithofacies Sr).

CSd geobodies, with up to 1.5 m of thickness and 100 m of lateral extension, are characterised by climbing ripples (Lithofacies Sc) and/or current rippled sandstones (Lithofacies Sr) at the base alternating with syn-sedimentary deformed sandstones (Lithofacies Sd). In addition, planar laminated siltstones (Lithofacies Ll) overlain by massive,

diffuse laminated siltstones and mudstones with pedogenic features (rhizoliths, mottles and cutans) plus desiccation cracks (Lithofacies Lm), occur at the distal limits of these geobodies (Fig. 4D).

CSp geobodies are interpreted as proximal crevasse-splay deposits. Lenticular bodies located within these geobodies, are interpreted as crevasse channel deposits. In contrast, CSd geobodies are interpreted as medial and distal crevasse-splay facies associations (Yeste et al., 2020). Also, as highlighted Yeste et al. (2020), CS geobodies rarely occur as a single crevasse-splay lobe. Rather they are formed during continuous flood events leading to overlapping CS geobodies, forming crevasse-splay complexes.

4.2.4 Geobody FP: floodplain deposits

FP geobodies are tabular in aspect, up to 10 m thick and may be up to 1000 m in lateral extent, with horizontal and sharp bounding surfaces (Table 1). These tabular bodies are characterised by massive mudstones (Lithofacies Fm) with abundant pedo-features (rhizoliths, mottles, nodules, cutans and slickensides). Locally, intervals, up to 2 m thick and with up to 100 m of lateral extension, characterised by thin-laminated mudstones (Lithofacies Fl), coal laminae and massive micritic limestones (Cm), also occur.

FP geobodies include distal floodplain (FA 9) and swamp (FA 10) facies associations as interpreted by Yeste et al. (2020). Massive mudstones with abundant pedo-features correspond to deposits of a distal floodplain. Intervals with laminated mudstones, coal laminae and massive micritic limestones are interpreted as deposits associated with swamp environments on the floodplain (Yeste et al., 2020).

4.3 Spatial relationship between geobodies and facies distribution

The full integration of both, outcrop and subsurface datasets, has enabled a significantly better understanding of the spatial relationships between described geobodies, as well as the development of conceptual models which include both descriptive and quantitative data related to the distribution of heterogeneities within the M-S Unit (Yeste et al., 2020). Key elements are summarised as follows (Fig. 5):

- Geobody CH is 40 m wide and up to 3 m thick. Geobodies PB and CS are genetically related with Geobody CH.
- On the accretional, inner margin of the channel thalweg, the CH geobody grades into the PB geobody. These are up to 3.6 m thick, and extend for up to 130 m, perpendicular to the main flow direction of the channel belt. The PB geobody extends from the main channel and grades laterally into the floodplain geobody (FP).
- On the erosive margin of the channel (CH), the CS geobodies comprise proximal crevasse-splay deposits (CSp), up to 2 m thick and with up to 130 m of lateral extension, perpendicular to the main flow direction of the channel belt, stretching from their insertion point on the channel margin. Geobody CSp passes from the channel into distal crevasse-splay deposits (CSd). These are similar in dimensions to CSp; up to 1.5 m thick, and with 100 m of lateral extension. The latter is located between 130 m and 230 m away from the main channel geobody and grades laterally into the FP geobody.

alt-text: Fig. 5

Fig. 5

Conceptual model of lateral variability for geobodies and facies including sedimentary features, lateral extent or width of the associated depositional area and thickness of each geobody (modified from Yeste et al., 2020).

In addition to the foregoing key observations, integrating both outcrop and subsurface data, and applying the quantitative conceptual model, a paleogeographic reconstruction was developed showing the distribution of the different geobodies for the selected interval (Fig. 6). This paleogeographic reconstruction will be used as a tool to test the results of geostatistical modelling in the following sections.

alt-text: Fig. 6

Fig. 6

Paleogeographic distribution of geobodies for the selected interval. This shows the location of both sedimentological sections and wells plus paleocurrent data.

5 Reservoir modelling: input data, methods and results

5.1 Input data, 3D model construction and methods

In the reservoir modelling process, the Petrel E&P software platform (developed and commercialized by Schlumberger) was used to build the 3D model. Data acquired from OBO characterisation, previously described, was used for both to define the geometry of the 3D model and to define the 3D distribution of geobodies (Fig. 7A and C).

alt-text: Fig. 7

Fig. 7

Three-dimensional geomodel framework, input data and geocellular outcrop model (GOM). (A) Layering model showing the 10 layers differentiated in the geomodel. (B) Cell dimensions established for the reservoir model framework. (C) Geolocated input data used in the modelling processes for this study, both from wells and sedimentological logs. (D) Geocellular outcrop model (GOM) of selected interval created from the digitizing of geobodies in the digital outcrop model (DOM). V.E. meaning vertical exaggeration. The coordinate reference system used was WGS84 UTM 30N.

The defined 3D model used two stratigraphic boundaries which correspond with both base and top of the selected interval. These stratigraphic boundaries were digitized as points and/or lines in the DOM and used as input data to the surface modelling process. In this process, a convergent interpolation method was used to extrapolate the digitized stratigraphic boundaries behind, as well as out of the outcrop, and generate the horizons that delimit both base and top of the 3D model. Convergent interpolation is a control point orientated algorithm which will converge upon the solution iteratively, adding more and more resolution with each iteration (Sbrana et al., 2018). This means that general trends are retained in areas with little data whilst detail is honoured in areas where the data exists. This is the common method used for surface and/or horizon modelling from line-data, dense point data, sparse point data or combinations of these data types; providing a stable extrapolation, even at large distances from the input data.

The dimensions selected for the 3D model are 1400 m × 1200 m × 5 m (Fig. 7A), comprising 1 zone and divided into 10 proportional layers (all layers between the base and top horizons of the zone are equally divided, showing the same thickness). The 3D cell dimensions are 5 m × 5 m × 0.5 m (Fig. 7B), resulting in a total of 672,000 cells for the 3D geomodel.

Two techniques were used for geostatistical modelling of facies distribution: object-based modelling and multi-point statistics-based modelling. Object-Based modelling (OBM) is a facies modelling technique aimed principally at

simulating the geometry of geological objects. This technique uses a stochastic simulation algorithm, the marked point process, to generate facies models (Holden et al., 1998). OBM offers the capability to model complex, well-defined facies objects as discrete bodies. OBM can readily incorporate geological concepts identified or interpreted from subsurface formations. In contrast, Multi-Point Statistics (MPS)-based modelling is a facies modelling technique that uses conceptual geological models as 3D training images (TI) to generate geologically realistic reservoir models conditioned by well data (Guardiano and Srivastava, 1993; Strebelle, 2002; Pyrcz et al., 2008; Daly and Caers, 2010; Mariethoz and Caers, 2015). It combines the ability to reproduce geological 'shapes', similar to object-based methods, with the speed and exact data-conditioning provided by variogram-based techniques. MPS extracts facies patterns from a conceptual TI that displays the facies elements believed to be present in the reservoir, and then reproduces in the model the patterns that fit the reservoir well data.

In this study, a combination of these two methods was used to obtain the reservoir modelling results. The OBM method was used to generate a 3D TI. In addition, during the process of designing and computing modelling workflows to generate the 3D TI, rule-based methods (Pyrcz et al., 2015) applying logical statement calculations, were used. Rule-based methods use rules to control the spatial position of geobodies and the facies population inside the geobodies. In order to establish how the 3D TI can help in the prediction of the reservoir geobodies, how the input data influence the predictions of the reservoir geobodies, as well as how this prediction adapts to the studied outcrop, the MPS method was used.

In addition, five scenarios were generated, based on the number of input data sources (wells and/or sedimentological logs). In each scenario, new input data were successively added, reducing the spacing between the hard data points (Fig. 8). For each scenario, 250 MPS realizations were generated.

Thus, in Scenario 1, the CP0 well, comprising a CH geobody, was used as the sole input data (Fig. 8A). Wells CP0 and MB4 were used in Scenario 2 (Fig. 8B). Both wells also penetrated a CH geobody. In Scenario 3, the CPML7 and CPMR7 wells, comprising CS_p and FP geobodies, were added to Wells CP0 and MB4 (Fig. 8C). In Scenario 4, the MB3 and CPML4 wells, characterized by PB geobodies, were added as compared to Scenario 3 (Fig. 8D). Finally, Scenario 5 used Wells CP0, CPMR5, CPMR7, CPMR8, CPML4, CPML7, CPML9, MB3, MB4, and CBML2 (Fig. 8E). Wells CPMR5 and CPML9 drilled CS_d and FP geobodies, whereas Wells CPMR8 and CBML2 are composed only of FP geobodies.

As interpreted, from the outcrop data, PB and CS geobodies are both linked to the CH geobody and thus provide information facilitating prediction of the location of the CH geobody. As such it would clearly be sufficient to obtain a reliable prediction for the CH geobody in order to establish the distribution of PB and CS geobodies. In addition, in order to establish the influence of input data containing PB and CS geobodies on the predicted location of the CH geobodies, only the calculation of CH probability, as outlined below, is required for better prediction. For this reason, the results shown in this study are focused on the prediction of the CH geobody.

After 250 MPS simulations for each scenario, a 3D probability volume for the CH geobody was built. This probability is defined, for a given cell, as the sum of the CH geobody population. In other words, a cell with a probability value of 20% means that from 250 realizations, the CH geobody populated the same cell in 50 realizations (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9

Calculation of the CH geobody probability. Left column shows three examples of the MPS realization for Scenario 2. Centre column shows the CH geobody population (red) from the MPS realization in a background (blue). Right column shows the sum of CH geobody populations after 250 MPS realizations for Scenario 2. [\(For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.\)](#)

Additionally, the paleogeographic reconstruction developed for the selected interval (Fig. 10A) shows that the orientation of the geobodies is not stationary. In other words, the orientation of the geobodies changes throughout the selected interval. In marked contrast, the TI generated for this study was built with a N-S orientation. To solve this peculiarity, an additional property was generated. This property shows the variation of azimuth trend throughout the selected interval. This azimuth trend property was used as an additional soft input data parameter that determines the general trend of geobodies, in order to obtain results which better match the conceptual model in the selected interval (Fig. 10B).

alt-text: Fig. 10

Fig. 10

(A) Paleogeographic reconstruction interpreted for the selected interval showing the azimuth trend line of the channel-belt interpreted in the selected interval, and (B) Azimuth trend property created from the azimuth trend line used as a mask in the MPS-based modelling process. Note also that in the MPS realizations of Fig. 9 how the azimuth trend property shown here clearly conditioned not the positions but rather the orientation of the geobodies.

Subsequently, a Geocellular Outcrop Model (GOM) was created from the digitized interpretations (geobody mapping) within the DOM (Fig. 7D). A GOM is a digital representation of the outcrop interpretation discretized into 3D cells. This digital representation includes the spatial distributions of geobodies, facies associations and/or facies, depending on the resolution of the outcrop interpretation. The first step in building a GOM is to digitize the outcrop interpretation in the DOM. This digitized outcrop interpretation is converted into a georeferenced point cloud. Each point in this

cloud stores interpretation information (geobody, facies association, facies) as an attribute, in addition to its spatial position. This point cloud with attributes is imported into the Petrel E&P software platform. The last step is to assign the attribute values of the points to the cells in the 3D grid (upscaling process). The digitizing of outcrop interpretations as well as the creation of a point cloud with attributes was carried out with the Virtual Reality Geological Studio (VRGS®) software (Hodgetts, 2010). The GOM is a useful tool with which to contrast the results obtained from geostatistical simulations, as well as to quantify the uncertainty associated with the results.

The GOM created for this study has a total of 306 upscaled cells and comprises outcrop sections studied in the previously described selected interval (Fig. 1C). This only includes data for the CH, PB and CS geobodies. The FP geobody was not included in the GOM as this non-reservoir element is used as the background in the modelling process.

To establish the accuracy of the modelling results compared with outcrop data, each MPS realization was compared with the GOM. To do this, the total number of cells in each realization which have the same value of CH, PB and CS geobodies, in comparison with the GOM cells, was calculated. For this study, this value has been termed as “Match”. The “Match” values are represented as a percentage.

5.2 Training image generation

The 3D Training Image (TI), used in this study was produced in a simple three-dimensional grid using horizontal surfaces as base and top. The dimensions of this simple grid are 1395 m × 1195 m × 5 m. It also comprises a single zone and 10 proportional layers. The 3D cell dimensions for this simple grid are 5 m × 5 m × 0.5 m. Thus, the TI has the same cell size as the 3D geomodel framework.

A modelling workflow was designed to populate the 3D reservoir model at geobody scale. Four different types of geobodies were interpreted in the studied M-S Unit. As previously described, these were (1) CH geobody, (2) PB geobody, (3) CS geobody, comprising finer scale CSp and CSd geobodies; and (4) FP geobody. The designed modelling workflow combines four different properties (bodies property, object-curvature property, directional trend property and insertion-zone property; Table 2) and two logical statements (LS 1 and LS 2; Table 2) to create the resultant geobodies model. The following section details the steps and calculations used for the representation of each geobody. The FP geobody was modelled as background.

alt-text: Table 2

Table 2

 The table layout displayed in this section is not how it will appear in the final version. The representation below is solely purposed for providing corrections to the table. To preview the actual presentation of the table, please view the Proof.

[Instruction: Please consider assembling the TABLE 2 better in the proof. Now it is difficult to understand.] Summary of the calculated properties and logical statements in the modelling workflow.

Calculated properties

Acronym	Property name	Description
<i>GM</i>	Geobodies model	Object-based modelling results representing geobody distribution (Fig. 13A).
<i>B_C</i>	Bodies property	Property with indexed numbers for each of the objects inserted from the object-based modelling result. The background facies are assigned to index number zero (Fig. 12A).
<i>CP</i>	Object-curvature property	Property whose values show the curvature of the edge of the nearest object. The curvature of the object's edge is calculated as the inverse of the radius of curvature of the edge, and made negative when the object is concave. The smallest radius of curvature is limited to one cell to avoid infinite curvature values when taking the inverse. The curvature away from the edge is calculated by using several nearby object-edge points, extrapolating the curvature, and then weighting by the inverse distance

		to the points. This causes the curvature values to asymptotically approach 0 away from objects (Fig. 12B).
DAP	Directional trend property	Property with the azimuth of the inserted bodies in each cell. For standard objects (eg. ellipse, box, pipe, lobe, etc.), the azimuth for each cell of the body is the same. However, for channel objects, the azimuth varies with the channel direction (Fig. 12D).
IZ	Insertion-zone property	Property calculated from object-curvature property of the channel object, and whose index numbers are 1, for the zone of highest curvature of the channel object, or 0 for the rest of object-curvature property of channel object. The value 1 representing the insertion zone of the CS geobodies (Fig. 12C).
Logical statements		
Acronym	Logical statement	Description
LS1	$GM = If (GM > 5 \text{ And } GM \leq 12, 2, GM)$	Assigns Lateral Accretion Packages (LAP) objects to a single PB geobody in the geobodies model (Fig. 11J). Values between 5 and 12 represent the LAPs geobodies (values 6 to 12 are Fig. 11A–J, respectively). Value 2 was assigned to PB geobody.
LS2	$IZ = If (CP > 0.14, 1, 0)$	Creates the insertion-zone property assigning the value 1 when channel curvature is > 0.14 , which represents the zone of highest curvature of the channel object; and the value 0 when channel curvature is < 0.14 (Fig. 12B–C).

The Channel geobody (CH), as previously described, is a channelized object, up to 3 m thick and up to 40 m in width. In addition, from a paleogeographic reconstruction of the selected interval, it is apparent that channel amplitude (up to 200 m) and wavelength (up to 400 m) can also be inferred (Fig. 6).

Point bar geobodies (PB) always occur on the inner margin of the thalweg so that the channel geobody grades into the point bar geobody. Internally, the PB geobody is characterised by lateral accretion packages (LAPs) formed by migration, typically by expansion and rotation, of the channel thalweg (Ghinassi et al., 2014; Ielpi and Ghinassi, 2014).

Considering this, PB geobodies have been modelled as successive channel objects to reproduce LAPs. Each channel object corresponds to a LAP. Each channel object also erodes the previous object and will be eroded by the next object (Fig. 11A–I). To reproduce the migration by expansion and rotation, each LAP increases its amplitude (to reproduce the expansion) and wavelength (to reproduce the rotation; Fig. 11). Finally, all LAPs are assigned to a PB geobody following the logical statement 1 (LS1; Fig. 11J; Table 2).

To model CS geobodies it is necessary to first obtain the curvature (CP) and directional trend properties of the channel geobody (Fig. 12A; Table 2). From the curvature property of the channel (Fig. 12B), and as CS geobodies occur on the erosive margin of the main channel, a property known as the “insertion-zone” (IZ) can be generated (Fig. 12C; Table 2). The highest positive values for the object-curvature property for a CH geobody correspond to the convex part of the channel object. Thus, the insertion-zone property is determined by the zone of highest curvature of the channel object. The object-curvature property for the CH geobody is associated with values higher than 0.14 for the insertion zone of CS geobodies. Within this framework, CS geobodies are generated when the insertion-zone property is characterized by values of 1, whereas for values of 0 no CS geobodies are generated. This key value is obtained with the logical statement 2 (LS2; Table 2). The directional trend property (DAP; Table 2) is used to determine the orientation of CS geobodies (Fig. 12D).

alt-text: Fig. 12

Fig. 12

(A) Channel object property, (B) Object-curvature property from channel object (A), (C) Insertion-zone property calculated from object-curvature property (B), (D) Directional trend property of channel object (A), and (E) CS geobodies modelling result.

alt-text: Fig. 13

Fig. 13

(A) 3D training image used in this study, created from the designed modelling workflow, (B)–(D) Comparison of interpreted digital outcrop models with similar vertical sections in the 3D TI. See (A) for location of vertical sections in the TI.

With this established, those objects corresponding to the CSd geobodies were first modelled. Subsequently, within these (CSd objects), the objects representing the CSp geobodies were then modelled. CSd objects have a width of up to 230 m and a thickness that varies between 0.8 and 2 m. CSp objects have a width of 130 m and a thickness of up to 2 m (Fig. 12E).

5.3 Analysis of the 3D training image

The modelling workflow, previously described, was used to populate the geobodies into the simple grid and create the 3D Training Image (Fig. 13A). This 3D training image was the basis for the MPS simulations presented in the next section.

Significantly, comparison of a similar vertical section from the TI with the DOM, in order to perform a qualitative analysis of the resulting TI, reproduced the distribution, geometry, dimensions and proportions of the interpreted sedimentary architecture. PB geobodies, for example, were always located on the accretional margin adjacent to the CH geobody. In addition, the TI also captured the asymmetrical-sigmoidal shape of the PB geobodies. CS geobodies were, in contrast, always modelled on the erosive margin of the CH geobody and the lobate shape of these geobodies was successfully reproduced. Furthermore, the overlapping lobe geobodies, giving rise to crevasse-splay complexes were also reproduced by the TI as well as the differentiation between Proximal (CSp) and Distal (CSd) CS geobodies (Fig. 13B–D).

In a plan view, the 3D TI also reproduced the distribution, geometry, dimensions and proportions of the conceptual model for the interpreted geobodies (Fig. 14). The CH object replicated the ribbon-like plan view geometry, as well as the crescent-shaped planform of PB geobodies and fan-shaped planform of CS geobodies.

Fig. 14

Comparison of the 2D conceptual model interpreted for the M-S Unit (A) with a plan view extracted from the TI created in this study (B).

5.4 Prediction of reservoir geobodies

A qualitative analysis of the probability results for CH geobody, for each scenario, is presented below:

Probability results in Scenario 1 showed the highest values (Probability values of >4%) around the channel-belt thalweg predicted in the paleogeographic reconstruction. Probability values higher than 20% were estimated near the wells and towards the southeast. However, MPS simulations overestimated probability values for the CH geobody in both the north-northeast and the south-west of the model (Fig. 15).

alt-text: Fig. 15

Fig. 15

Probability results for CH geobody prediction in each scenario. The left-hand column shows the paleogeographic reconstruction for selected interval (Fig. 7). The middle column shows the 3D probability volume for the CH geobody. Right hand column shows the 3D probability volume for the CH geobody with probability values of <10 filtered.

In Scenario 2, results from the MPS simulations also show the highest probability values (Probability values of >4%) around the predicted channel-belt thalweg. Probability values higher than 20% were estimated only near the wells, in this case. MPS simulations also overestimated probability values for the CH geobody in the north-northeast and in the south-west of the model (Fig. 15).

In contrast to scenarios 1 and 2, probability results in Scenario 3 do not show the highest values (Probability values of >4%) around the complete predicted channel-belt thalweg. In addition, MPS simulations overestimated probability values for the CH geobody over a more extended area towards the northeast when compared with the previous scenarios. Probability values of >20% were obtained only near Wells CP0 and MB4. In contrast, Wells CPML7 and CPMR7 are characterized by CS geobodies. Consequently, the addition of these wells helps to better constrain the highest probability values for the location of the CH geobody location in outcrop (Wells CP0 and MB4). However, in contrast, the addition of Well CPMR7 does seem to have produced an increase of overestimated probability values for the CH geobody towards the northeast of the model grid, when compared with the previous scenarios (Fig. 15).

Scenario 4 generated a similar distribution for the highest probability values compared to Scenario 3. MPS simulations decreased the overestimated probability values for the CH geobody towards the east compared to Scenario 3.

Probability values higher than 20% were also obtained near Wells CP0 and MB4, although the area for these probability values increased compared to Scenario 3 (Fig. 15).

MPS simulations of Scenario 5 decreased the overestimated model area for CH geobody probability values towards the east, compared to Scenarios 3 and 4. Probability values higher than 20% were also obtained near Wells CP0 and MB4, and with a similar area, when compared to Scenario 4 (Fig. 15).

In summary, all scenarios showed an overestimation of CH geobody prediction, both in the northeast and southwest of the model. However, it is also worthy of note that the highest probability values are associated with the area suggested by the paleogeographic reconstruction. On the other hand, an increase in input data, even though these additional wells do not contain a CH geobody, clearly serves to constrain the highest probability values for the location of the CH geobody, although this appears to have been at the expense of generating an increase of overestimated probability values in other zones of the model. These overestimated probability values are produced because input data are not available in this part of the model and, thus, the algorithm has a high degree of freedom resulting in the repetition of the mathematical pattern. In addition, the size of the mathematical pattern (TI) probably also induces these overestimated values in other zones of the model.

5.5 Uncertainty analysis

Match results show that, in Scenario 1, with data input only from Well CP0, match values range from 3% to 41%, with a mean value of 15% (Fig. 15, Table 3). Adding one new source of input data, Well MB4, increased mean match values by 11%, according to results obtained in Scenario 2. This showed match values ranging from 5% to 46%, with a mean value of 26% (Fig. 16A, Table 3). Both scenarios are characterized by the presence of the CH geobody.

alt-text: Table 3

Table 3

i The table layout displayed in this section is not how it will appear in the final version. The representation below is solely purposed for providing corrections to the table. To preview the actual presentation of the table, please view the Proof.

Number of input wells, input upscaled cells and match values for each scenario. The upscaled cells from input wells column represents the total number of upscaled cells used as input data for each scenario. Minimum (Min), maximum (Max) and mean match values are shown. The standard deviation (Std), P10 and P90 match values also are presented, based on 250 realizations.

Scenario	Input wells	upscaled cells from wells	Match (%)					
			Min	Max	Mean	Std	P10	P90
1	1	10	3	41	15	6.0	8	23
2	2	20	5	46	26	8.4	15	38
3	4	40	12	51	29	6.9	19	37
4	6	60	24	56	40	5.5	33	47
5	10	90	31	62	44	5.7	37	52

alt-text: Fig. 16

Fig. 16

(A) Plot showing the cumulative match frequency for the five scenarios. Note how the cumulative frequency curve shifts to higher match values with increasing input data. The highest shift of the cumulative frequency curve towards higher match values occurs in Scenarios 2 and 4. The curve with the steepest slope occurs in Scenario 4, indicating a lower dispersion in match values in this scenario compared to the others. (B) Plot of upscaled cells from wells versus match for each scenario. P10, P50 and P90 match values, based on 250 realizations per scenario, are plotted (see Table 3).

In Scenario 3, two new wells, CPML7 and CPMR7, were added. These wells are characterized by CS_p, CS_d and FP geobodies. Scenario 3 showed match values ranging from 12% to 51%, with a mean value of 29% (Fig. 16A, Table 3). However, despite adding two new data points, this scenario only increased mean match values by 3% compared to Scenario 2.

Scenario 4 showed match values ranging from 24% to 56%, with a mean value of 40% (Fig. 16A, Table 3). In this scenario Wells MB3 and CPML4 were added to the model, both of which are characterized by PB geobodies. Scenario 4, in contrast to Scenario 3 showed a notably more significant increase in the mean match value of 11%.

Finally, adding four new wells in Scenario 5, characterized by both CS_d and FP geobodies, resulted in the mean match value increasing by 4% compared to Scenario 4. Match values range from 31% to 62%, with a mean value of 44% (Fig. 16A, Table 3).

The results of the match process for the five scenarios, described above, show a linear relationship between the number of upscaled cells (input data), used to create the simulation, and the match (Fig. 16B). However, the highest increases in match values were observed in Scenarios 2 and 4, where the match increased by 11% in both cases, compared to Scenarios 1 and 3, respectively. Scenario 2 added as new input data, one well (MB4) characterized by a CH geobody, whilst Scenario 4 added two wells characterized by PB geobodies. Scenarios 3 and 5 also increased match values but these match increases were only of 3%, in Scenario 3, and 4%, in Scenario 5, compared to Scenarios 2 and 4, respectively. Both scenarios 3 and 5, added, as new input data, wells characterized by CS and FP geobodies.

In summary, match results showed an increase in match values for all scenarios, but this increase was more substantial when the input data were characterized by CH and PB geobodies (scenarios 2 and 4) in comparison to cases in which input data are characterized by only CS and FP geobodies (scenarios 3 and 5; Fig. 16). Furthermore, standard deviation (Std) generally decreases as the number of upscaled cells from wells increases (Table 3), reflecting the importance of additional wells in reducing uncertainty.

6 Discussion

The present study highlights the use of outcrop analogues in reservoir modelling of fluvial systems (Pringle et al., 2006; Enge et al., 2007; Hodgetts, 2013; Howell et al., 2014; Colombera et al., 2016; Cabello et al., 2018). This integrated study of outcrop and subsurface data has allowed the generation of quantitative conceptual models which have proven extremely useful in geostatistical modelling. This is especially so when it comes to planning modelling strategies as well as producing training images. In addition, recent technical advances in digital outcrop characterization and data capture have proven to be a valuable tool, allowing precise uncertainty analysis of the modelling results.

Recent studies clearly indicate the usefulness of digital outcrop models in reservoir modelling, as well as, in the generation of 3D training images by integrating spatial information obtained directly from outcrop measurements (Dimitrakopoulos et al., 2010; Boucher, 2011; Pickel et al., 2015; Cabello et al., 2018; Puig et al., 2019; Mitten et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2021a,b). Current common techniques used in the construction of reservoir models are OBM (Object-Based Modelling) or SIS (Sequential-Indicator Simulation) methods, a reflection of the inherent complexities typically associated with generating the appropriate training images required for MPS modelling techniques.

In attempts to resolve this issue, several authors have used DOM data to generate 2D TIs (eg., Comunian et al., 2012; Pickel et al., 2015). These TIs demonstrated a clear vertical facies trend but did not well represent the 3D facies pattern. An alternative approach to constructing a TI is the OBM method as proposed by other authors (e.g., Pyrcz et al., 2008; Bezrukov and Davletova, 2010; Gottschalk et al., 2017; Tahmasebi, 2018). Mitten et al. (2020) to combine information from DOMs, to represent vertical facies patterns (Z dimension), and satellite images to represent the other two dimensions (X and Y). However, this manual development of training images is laborious, as it requires multiple iterations and manual checks of intersectional planes throughout the training image volume and target fractions to ensure that input statistics are honoured. In addition, they are difficult to export to other similar environments with different distribution, geometry, dimensions and proportions.

The current study combines the information obtained from both outcrop and subsurface data with the OBM methodology to create a 3D TI from the designed modelling workflow (Fig. 2). The resulting 3D TI represents the geobody distribution, orientation and geometry described in the studied outcrop, as well as the spatial relationships between geobodies (Figs. 13 and 14). Both 3D TI and modelling workflow are directly exportable to any similar reservoir, even if the scale of fluvial system is different, only by establishing the dimensional parameters of the geobodies that make up this reservoir.

Using the TI, subsequent MPS simulations generated reliable predictions for the CH geobody, although all scenarios showed an overestimation both in the northeast and southwest sectors of the model. This overestimation was, however, expected as a response to: (a) the spatial relationships between the geobodies generated in the TI, as the MPS algorithm looks for the repetition of the mathematical pattern from the TI, so that when the model is far away from the input data, the algorithm is ruled by just the TI pattern; and (b) the dimensions of the TI, because in a TI with larger dimensions the percentage of the CH geobody would be lower and it would possibly reduce this overestimation by reproducing background facies (floodplain deposits) in the areas where CH geobody was overestimated. Even so, these overestimations can be ruled out as soon as logical criteria are applied, such as the confidence radius of input data, continuity of probability trends related to input data and/or continuity lack of input data. However, despite these issues, the highest probability values still occur in the area suggested by the paleogeographic reconstruction (Fig. 15).

Increasing the amount of input data in the model, located close to the target (CH geobody), showed a match increase (Fig. 16A). On the other hand, although the additional wells did not penetrate the CH geobody but rather, PB or CS geobodies; they still play an important role in the MPS simulations, increasing the match and delimiting the probability zones with greater confidence (Fig. 16A).

On the basis of the results obtained in this study, in a hypothetical appraisal stage, even in these low net-to-gross reservoirs, a large number of wells would not be necessary to predict reservoir geobodies, in which our precision is expected to increase quickly with each new well (Fig. 16). This high level of prediction would thus help in the design of an optimized development drilling program.

7 Conclusions

The current study, integrating both outcrop and subsurface data, has successfully demonstrated the application of outcrop analogues as a basis for informing, designing and testing predictive tools for forecasting the reservoir

architecture of high-sinuosity fluvial successions in the subsurface.

The outcrop/behind outcrop methodology has allowed the generation of quantitative conceptual models useful in geostatistical modelling. This is especially so, when it comes to planning modelling strategies as well as producing training images. High-Resolution Digital Outcrop Models (DOMs) have proven to be a useful tool in geostatistical modelling. The DOMs help to incorporate more geological data (Digitized facies, geometric data, the relationships between facies distributions, virtual sedimentological logs, etc.) into the modelling process allowing us to generate more robust geostatistical models. These then provide the necessary data to obtain a Geocellular Outcrop Model (GOM) and thereby have a greater control over the results obtained.

The modelling workflow designed for this study has successfully reproduced the distribution of heterogeneities interpreted within the M-S Unit at geobody scale. This modelling workflow is potentially exportable to other examples of this type of reservoir, for the development of training images and/or directly for use in the reservoir facies modelling.

Probability models obtained from MPS simulations, and using the 3D training image created for this study, generated a good prediction of the channel geobody throughout the model framework. This was in agreement with the paleogeographic reconstruction, even when considering a scenario in which only one well drilled the channel. MPS simulation results also showed mean match values ranging from 15% to 44%, depending on the scenario considered.

The applied workflow helps to optimize the value of the information obtained from each well, reducing the uncertainty in the location of the geobodies, which is essential when designing a development or infill drilling program in a field.

Credit author statement

Luis Miguel Yeste: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Ricardo Palomino:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Augusto Nicolás Varela:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Neil David McDougall:** Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **César Viseras:** Investigation, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

Funding was provided by the research project [CGL 2017-89618-R \(AEI/FEDER, UE\)](#), the RNM369 Research Group (PAI) and by the Repsol-[University of Granada](#) agreement. The research stay of A.N. Varela was funded by the Coimbra Group Young Latin American Professor Scholarship and Argentinean [National Research Council \(CONICET\)](#) External Research Scholarship. The authors are indebted to Schlumberger, for providing the academic license 2-1394908 for Petrel software, and David Hodgetts for providing the academic licence of VRGS software. The authors also thank REPSOL EXPLORACION, CEPESA E.P and Crimidesa for their support. We thank the constructive reviews of both anonymous reviewers.

References

 The corrections made in this section will be reviewed and approved by a journal production editor. The newly added/removed references and its citations will be reordered and rearranged by the production team.

Allen, J.R.L., 1963. The classification of cross-stratified units, with notes on their origin. *Sedimentology* 2, 93–114.

Anderson, M.P., 1989. Hydrogeologic facies models to delineate large-scale spatial trends in glacial and glaciofluvial sediments. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 4 (101), 501–511. doi:10.1130/0016-

- Arche, A., López-Gómez, J., 2014. The carnian pluvial event in western europe: new data from iberia and correlation with the western neotethys and eastern north America–nw africa regions. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 128, 196–231.
- Bezrukov, A., Davletova, A.R., 2010. Implementation Prospects of Multi-point Statistics Methods into the Practice of Geological Modeling: Society of Petroleum Engineers Russian Oil and Gas Conference and Exhibition, 26–28 Oct., 2010. SPE-135911-MS, Moscow, Russia, p. 5. doi:10.2118/135911-MS.
- Boucher, A., 2011. Strategies for Modeling with Multiple-point Simulation Algorithms, Closing the Gap: Advances in Applied Geomodeling for Hydrocarbon Reservoirs. Canadian Society of Petroleum Geologists, Calgary, pp. 67–73.
- Bridge, J.S., 1993. Description and interpretation of fluvial deposits: a critical perspective. *Sedimentology* 40, 801–810.
- Bridge, J.S., 2003. *Rivers and Floodplains: Forms, Processes, and Sedimentary Record*. Blackwell Publishing, Malden, p. 491.
- Bryant, I.D., Carr, D., Cirilli, P., Drinkwater, N., McCormick, D., Tilke, P., Thurmond, J., 2000. Use of 3D digital analogues as templates in reservoir modelling. *Petrol. Geosci.* 6, 195–201.
- Cabello, P., Domínguez, D., Murillo-López, M.H., López-Blanco, M., García-Sellés, D., Cuevas, J.L., Marzo, M., Arbués, P., 2018. From conventional outcrop datasets and digital outcrop models to flow simulation in the Pont de Montanyana point-bar deposits (Ypresian, Southern Pyrenees). *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 94, 19–42. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2018.03.040.
- Caers, J., Zhang, T., 2004. Multiple-point Geostatistics: a quantitative vehicle for integrating geologic analogs into multiple reservoir models. In: *Integration of Outcrop and Modern Analogs in Reservoir Modelling*, vol. 80. AAPG Memoir, pp. 383–394.
- Clemetsen, R., Hurst, A.R., Knarud, R., Omre, H., 1990. A computer program for evaluation of fluvial reservoirs May 8–11, 1989 In: Buller, A.T., Berg, E., Hjemeland, O., Kleppe, J., Torsaeter, O., Aasen, J.O. (Eds.), *North Sea Oil and Gas Reservoirs—II: 2nd North Sea Oil and Gas Reservoirs Conference*, Trondheim, Norway. pp. 373–385. doi:10.1007/978-94-009-0791-1_32.
- Colombera, L., Mountney, N.P., Howell, J.A., Rittersbacher, A., Felletti, F., McCaffrey, W.D., 2016. A test of analog-based tools for quantitative prediction of large-scale fluvial architecture. *AAPG (Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol.) Bull.* 100 (2), 237–267. doi:10.1306/11181514227.
- Comunian, A., Renard, P.N., Straubhaar, J., 2012. 3D multiple-point statistics simulation using 2D training images. *Comput. Geosci.* 40, 49–65. doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2011.07.009.
- Dabrio, C., Fernández, J., Viseras, C., 2005. Triassic fluvial sandstones (central south Spain) – an excellent analogue for the TAGI reservoir of Algeria. In: *67th European Association of Geoscientists and Engineers Conference and Exhibition. Field Trip Guide Incorporating SPEEUROPEC 2005*, 13–16 June 2005. IFEMA, Madrid, Spain.
- Daly, C., Caers, J., 2010. Multi-point geostatistics – an introductory overview. *First Break* 28, 39–47.
- Davis, J.M., Wilson, J.L., Phillips, F.M., Gotkowitz, M.B., 1997. Relationship between fluvial bounding surfaces and the permeability correlation structure. *Water Resour. Res.* 33 (8), 1843–1854. doi:10.1029/97WR01003.
- Deschamps, R., Guy, N., Preux, C., Lerat, O., 2012. Analysis of heavy oil recovery by thermal EOR in a meander melt: from geological to reservoir modeling. *Oil Gas Sci. Technol. - Rev. IFP Energies nouvelles* 67, 883–1039. doi:10.2516/ogst/2012015.

- Deutsch, C.V., 2002. *Geostatistical Reservoir Modelling: Applied Geostatistics Series*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Deutsch, C.V., Tran, T.T., 2002. FLUVSIM: a program for object-based stochastic modeling of fluvial depositional systems. *Comput. Geosci.* 28 (4), 525–535. doi:10.1016/S0098-3004(01)00075-9.
- Deutsch, C.V., Wang, L., 1996. Quantifying object-based stochastic modeling of fluvial reservoirs. *Math. Geol.* 28 (7), 857–880.
- Deutsch, C.V., Journal, A., 1992. *GSLIB. Geostatistical Software Library and User's Guide*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Dimitrakopoulos, R., Mustapha, H., Gloaguen, E., 2010. High-order statistics of spatial random fields: exploring spatial cumulants for modeling complex non-Gaussian and non-linear phenomena. *Math. Geosci.* 42 (1), 65–99. doi:10.1007/s11004-009-9258-9.
- Donselaar, M.E., Schmidt, J.M., 2005. Integration of outcrop and borehole image logs for high-resolution facies interpretation: example from a fluvial fan in the Ebro Basin, Spain. *Sedimentology* 52, 1021–1042.
- Enge, H.E., Buckley, S.J., Rotevatn, A., Howell, J.A., 2007. From outcrop to reservoir simulation model: workflow and procedures. *Geosphere* 3, 469–490. doi:10.1130/GES00099.1.
- Falivene, O., Arbues, P., Gardiner, A., Pickup, G., Munoz, J.A., Cabrera, L., 2006. Best practice stochastic facies modeling from a channel-fill turbidite sandstone analog (the Quarry outcrop, Eocene Ainsa basin, northeast Spain). *AAPG (Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol.) Bull.* 90 (7), 1003–1029. doi:10.1306/02070605112.
- Fernández, J., 1977. *Sedimentación triásica en el borde Sureste de la Meseta* PhD dissertation Universidad de Granada, p. 173.
- Fernández, J., Dabrio, C., 1985. Fluvial architecture of the buntsandstein-facies redbeds in the middle to upper triassic (Ladinian–Norian) of the southeastern edge of the Iberian Meseta (southern Spain). In: Mader, D. (Ed.), *Aspects of Fluvial Sedimentation in the Lower Triassic Buntsandstein of Europe*. In: *Lecture Notes in Earth Sciences*, vol. 4. pp. 411–435.
- Ford, G.L., Pyles, D.R., 2014. A hierarchical approach for evaluating fluvial systems: architectural analysis and sequential evolution of the high net-sand content, middle Wasatch Formation, Uinta Basin, Utah. *AAPG (Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol.) Bull.* 98, 1273–1304.
- García-García, F., Yeste, L.M., Henares, S., Viseras, C., 2017. Tides and Waves Influence Variability on the Shoreline Systems of the Heterolithic Unit from the Triassic Tabular Cover of the Iberian Meseta. 33rd IAS Meeting of Sedimentology, 10-12 Oct 2017, Toulouse - France.
- Gaud, M.N., Smith, G.A., McKenna, S.A., 2004. Relating small-scale permeability heterogeneity to Lithofacies distribution. In: Bridge, J., Hyndman, D.W. (Eds.), *Aquifer Characterization*, vol. 80. SEPM, Special Publication, pp. 55–66.
- Ghinassi, M., Nemeč, W., Aldinucci, M., Nehyba, S., Özaksoy, V., Fiolini, F., 2014. Planform evolution of ancient meandering rivers reconstructed from longitudinal outcrop sections. *Sedimentology* 61, 952–977.
- Gottschalk, I.P., Hermans, T., Knight, R., Caers, J., Cameron, D.A., Regnery, J., McCray, J.E., 2017. Integrating non colocated well and geophysical data to capture subsurface heterogeneity at an aquifer recharge and recovery site. *J. Hydrol.* 555, 407–419. doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.10.028.
- Guardiano, F., Srivastava, R., 1993. Multivariate geostatistics: beyond bivariate moments. In: Soares, A. (Ed.), *Geostatistics Troia 1992*. Kluwer, Dordrecht, pp. 133–144.
- Henares, S., Caracciolo, L., Cultrone, G., Fernández, J., Viseras, C., 2014. The role of diagenesis and depositional facies on pore system evolution in a Triassic outcrop analogue (SE Spain). *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 51, 136–151.

- Henares, S., Caracciolo, L., Viseras, C., Fernández, J., Yeste, L.M., 2016. Diagenetic constraints on heterogeneous reservoir quality assessment: a Triassic outcrop analogue of meandering fluvial reservoirs. *AAPG (Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol.) Bull.* 100 (9), 1377–1398.
- Hodgetts, D., 2010. Collection, processing, interpretation and modelling of digital outcrop data using VRGS: an integrated approach to outcrop modelling. In: Presented at the 72nd EAGE Conference and Exhibition. Workshops and Fieldtrips, Barcelona, Spain. doi:10.3997/2214-4609.20149961.
- Hodgetts, D., 2013. Laser scanning and digital outcrop geology in the petroleum industry: a review. *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 46, 335–354. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2013.02.014.
- Holden, L., Hauge, R., Skare, O., Skorstad, A., 1998. Modeling of fluvial reservoirs with object models. *Math. Geol.* 30, 473–496.
- Howell, J.A., Martinius, A.W., Good, T.R., 2014. The application of outcrop analogues in geological modelling: a review, present status and future outlook. In: Martinius, A.W., Howell, J.A., Good, T.R. (Eds.), *Sediment-Body Geometry and Heterogeneity: Analogue Studies for Modelling the Subsurface*, vol. 387. Geological Society of London, Special Publications, pp. 1–25. doi:10.1144/SP387.12.
- Hu, L.Y., Liu, Y., Scheepens, C., Shultz, A.W., Thompson, R.D., 2014. Multiple-point simulation with an existing reservoir model as training image. *Math. Geol.* 46, 227–240. doi:10.1007/s11004-013-9488-8.
- Ielpi, A., Ghinassi, M., 2014. Planform architecture, stratigraphic signature and morphodynamics of an exhumed Jurassic meander plain (Scalby Formation, Yorkshire, UK). *Sedimentology* 61, 1923–1960.
- Klingbeil, R., Kleineidam, S., Asprion, U., Aigner, T., Teutsch, G., 1999. Relating Lithofacies to hydrofacies: outcrop-based hydrogeological characterization of quaternary gravel deposits. *Sediment. Geol.* 129 (3–4), 299–310. doi:10.1016/S0037-0738(99)00067-6.
- Koltermann, C.E., Gorelick, S.M., 1996. Heterogeneity in sedimentary deposits: a review of structure-imitating, process-imitating, and descriptive approaches. *Water Resour. Res.* 32 (9), 2617–2658. doi:10.1029/96WR00025.
- Kostic, B., Aigner, T., 2007. Sedimentary architecture and 3D ground-penetrating radar analysis of gravelly meandering river deposits (Neckar Valley, SW Germany). *Sedimentology* 54, 789–808.
- Krum, G.L., Johnson, C.R., 1993. A 3-D modelling approach for providing a complex reservoir descriptions for reservoir simulations. In: Flint, S.S., Bryant, I.D. (Eds.), *The Geological Modelling of Hydrocarbon Reservoirs and Outcrop Analogues*, vol. 15. International Association of Sedimentologists, Special Publications, pp. 253–258.
- Le Coz, M., Genthon, P., Adler, P.M., 2011. Multiple-point statistics for modelling facies heterogeneities in a porous medium: the Komadugu-Yobe alluvium, Lake Chad Basin. *Math. Geol.* 43, 861–878. doi:10.1007/s11004-011-9353-6.
- López-Gómez, J., et al., 2019. Permian-triassic rifting stage. In: Quesada, C., Tomás Oliveira, J. (Eds.), *The Geology of Iberia: A Geodynamic Approach*. Springer. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-11295-0.
- Ma, Y.Z., 2019. Quantitative Geosciences: Data Analytics, Geostatistics, Reservoir Characterization and Modeling. Springer, p. 664, 978-3-030-17859-8.
- Maharaja, A., 2008. TiGenerator: object-based training image generator. *Comput. Geosci.* 34 (12), 1753–1761. doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2007.08.012.
- Mariethoz, G., Caers, J., 2015. *Multiple-point Geostatistics*. Wiley Blackwell, Chichester.
- Martinius, A.W., Fustic, M., Garner, D.L., Jablonski, B.V.J., Strobl, R.S., MacEachern, J.A., Dashtgard, S.E., 2017. Reservoir characterization and multiscale heterogeneity modelling of inclined heterolithic strata for bitumen-production forecasting, McMurray Formation, Corner, Alberta, Canada. *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 82, 336–361. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2017.02.003.

- Miall, A.D., 1985. Architectural-element analysis: a new method of facies analysis applied to fluvial deposits. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 22, 261–308.
- Mitten, A.J., Mullins, J., Pringle, J.K., Howell, J., Clarke, S.M., 2020. Depositional conditioning of three dimensional training images: improving the reproduction and representation of architectural elements in sand dominated fluvial reservoir models. *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 113, 104156. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2019.104156.
- Pickel, A., Frechette, J.D., Comunian, A., Weissmann, G.S., 2015. Building a training image with digital outcrop models. *J. Hydrol.* 531, 53–61. doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2015.08.049.
- Pranter, M.J., Sommer, N.K., 2011. Static connectivity of fluvial sandstones in a lower coastalplain setting: an example from the upper cretaceous lower Williams fork formation, Piceance Basin, Colorado. *AAPG (Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol.) Bull.* 95, 899–923. doi:10.1306/12091010008.
- Pringle, J.K., Howell, J.A., Hodgetts, D., Westerman, A.R., Hodgson, D.M., 2006. Virtual outcrop models of petroleum reservoir analogues: a review of the current state-of-the-art. *First Break* 24, 33–42.
- Puig, J.M., Cabello, P., Howell, J., Arbués, P., 2019. Three-dimensional characterisation of sedimentary heterogeneity and its impact on subsurface flow behaviour through the braided-to-meandering fluvial deposits of the Castissent Formation (late Ypresian, Tremp-Graus Basin, Spain). *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 103, 661–680. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2019.02.014.
- Pyrzcz, M.J., Boisvert, J.B., Deutsch, C.V., 2008. A library of training images for fluvial and deepwater reservoirs and associated code. *Comput. Geosci.* 34 (5), 542–560. doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2007.05.015.
- Pyrzcz, M.J., Sech, R.P., Covault, J.A., Willis, B.J., Sylvester, Z., Sun, T., 2015. Stratigraphic rule-based reservoir modeling. *Bull. Can. Petrol. Geol.* 63 (4), 287–303. doi:10.2113/gscpgbull.63.4.287.
- Rarity, F., Van Laen, X.M.T., Hodgetts, D., Gawthorpe, R.L., Wilson, P., Fabuel-Perez, I., Redfern, J., 2014. LiDAR-based digital outcrops for sedimentological analysis: workflows and techniques. In: Martinus, A.W., Howell, J.A., Good, T. (Eds.), *Sediment-Body Geometry and Heterogeneity: Analogue Studies for Modelling the Subsurface*. Geological Society of London, Special Publications, p. 387. doi:10.1144/SP387.5.
- Rossi, C., Kälin, O., Arribas, J., Tortosa, A., 2002. Diagenesis, provenance and reservoir quality of triassic TAGI sandstones from ourhoud field, berkine (ghadames) basin, Algeria. *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 19, 117–142.
- Sbrana, A., Marianelly, P., Pasquini, G., Costantini, P., Palmieri, F., Ciani, V., Sbrana, M., 2018. The integration of 3D modeling and simulation to determine the energy potential of low-temperature geothermal systems in the Pisa (Italy) sedimentary plain. *Energies* 11, 1591. doi:10.3390/en11061591.
- Seifert, D., Jensen, J.L., 1999a. Using sequential indicator simulation as a tool in reservoir description: issues and uncertainties. *Math. Geol.* 31 (5), 527–550. doi:10.1023/A:1007563907124.
- Seifert, D., Jensen, J.L., 1999b. Using sequential indicator simulation as a tool in reservoir description: issues and uncertainties. *Math. Geol.* 31 (5), 527–550. doi:10.1023/A:1007563907124.
- Seifert, D., Jensen, J.L., 2000a. Object and pixel-based reservoir modelling of a braided fluvial reservoir. *Math. Geol.* 32 (5), 581–603. doi:10.1023/A:1007562221431.
- Seifert, D., Jensen, J.L., 2000b. Object and pixel-based reservoir modelling of a braided fluvial reservoir. *Math. Geol.* 32 (5), 581–603. doi:10.1023/A:1007562221431.
- Slatt, R.M., Buckner, N., Abousleiman, Y., Sierra, R., Philp, P., Miceli-Romero, A., Portas, R., O'Brien, N., Tran, M., Davis, R., Wawrzyniec, T., 2012. Outcrop/behind outcrop (quarry), multiscale characterization of the Woodford gas shale, Oklahoma. In: Breyer, J. (Ed.), *Shale Reservoirs: Giant Resources for the 21st Century*, vol. 97. AAPG Memoirs, pp. 1–21.
- Strebelle, S., 2002. Conditional simulation of complex geological structures using multiple-point statistics. *Math. Geol.* 34, 1–22.

- Strebelle, S., Levy, M., 2008. Using multiple-point statistics to build geologically realistic reservoir models: the MPS/FDM workflow. In: Robinson, A., Griffiths, P., Price, S., Hegre, J., Muggeridge, A. (Eds.), *The Future of Geological Modelling in Hydrocarbon Development*, vol. 309. Geological Society Special Publications, pp. 67–74. doi:10.1144/SP309.5.
- Tahmasebi, P., 2018. Multiple point statistics: a review. In: Daya Sagar, B., Cheng, Q., Agterberg, F. (Eds.), *Handbook of Mathematical Geosciences*. Springer, Cham. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-78999-6_30.
- Thomas, H., Brigaud, B., Blaise, T., Saint-Bezar, B., Zordan, E., Zeyen, H., Andrieu, S., Vicent, B., Chirol, H., Portier, E., Mouche, E., 2021a. Contribution of drone photogrammetry to 3D outcrop modeling of facies, porosity, and permeability heterogeneities in carbonate reservoirs (Paris Basin, Middle Jurassic). *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 123, 104772. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2020.104772.
- Thomas, H., Brigaud, B., Blaise, T., Saint-Bezar, B., Zordan, E., Zeyen, H., Andrieu, S., Vicent, B., Chirol, H., Portier, E., Mouche, E., 2021b. Contribution of drone photogrammetry to 3D outcrop modeling of facies, porosity, and permeability heterogeneities in carbonate reservoirs (Paris Basin, Middle Jurassic). *Mar. Petrol. Geol.* 123, 104772. doi:10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2020.104772.
- Thomas, R.G., Smith, D.G., Wood, J.M., Visser, J., Calverley- Range, E.A., Koster, E.H., 1987. Inclined heterolithic stratification-terminology, description, interpretation and significance. *Sediment. Geol.* 53, 123–179.
- Viseras, C., Fernández, J., Henares, S., 2011. Facies Architecture in Outcropping Analogues for the TAGI Reservoir. Exploratory Interest. AAPG International Conference and Exhibition, Search and Discovery Article, #90135, Milan, Italy.
- Viseras, C., Henares, S., Yeste, L.M., Garcia-Garcia, F., 2018. Reconstructing the architecture of ancient meander belts by compiling outcrop and subsurface data: a Triassic example. In: Ghinassi, M., Colombera, L., Mountney, N.P., Reesink, A.J.H. (Eds.), *Fluvial Meanders and Their Sedimentary Products in the Rock Record*, vol. 48. IAS Special Publication, pp. 419–444. doi:10.1002/9781119424437.ch16.
- Weissmann, G.S., Fogg, G.E., 1999. Multi-scale alluvial fan heterogeneity modelled with transition probability geostatistics in a sequence stratigraphic framework. *J. Hydrol.* 226 (1–2), 48–65. doi:10.1016/S0022-1694(99)00160-2.
- Yeste, L.M., García-García, F., McDougall, N.D., Henares, S., Viseras, C., 2017. Tidal vs Fluvial Point Bars: Key Features Which Differentiate Them in Outcrops, Core and Wireline Logs. 33rd IAS Meeting of Sedimentology, 10-12 Oct 2017, Toulouse, France.
- Yeste, L.M., Henares, S., McDougall, N., García-García, F., Viseras, C., 2019. Towards the multi-scale characterization of braided fluvial geobodies from outcrop, core, georadar and well logs data. In: Corbett, P., Owen, A., Hartley, A., Pla-Pueyo, S., Barreto, D., Hackney, C., Kape, S. (Eds.), *River to Reservoir: Geoscience to Engineering*. GSL Special Publication, p. 488. doi:10.1144/sp488.3.
- Yeste, L.M., Varela, A.N., Viseras, C., Mcdougall, N.D., García-García, F., 2020. Reservoir architecture and heterogeneity distribution in floodplain sandstones: key features in outcrop, core and wireline logs. *Sedimentology* 67 (7), 3355–3388. doi:10.1111/sed.12747.
- Zhou, F., Shields, D., Tyson, S., Esterle, J., 2018. Comparison of sequential indicator simulation, object modelling and multiple-point statistics in reproducing channel geometries and continuity in 2D with two different spaced conditional datasets. *J. Petrol. Sci. Eng.* 166, 718–730. doi:10.1016/j.petrol.2018.03.043.